

DEVELOPMENT OF STUDENTS' CRITICAL THINKING SKILLS IN
ENGLISH LANGUAGE LESSONS

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Abstract: This article discusses the importance of wide use of activities that develop critical thinking in English language classes. As a result of the use of modern approaches and innovative methods, such as the development of critical thinking in English language teaching, the development of students' logical thinking skills, fluency in speech, the formation of quick and correct response skills, instilling enthusiasm for knowledge and the English language lessons about the importance of a creative approach.

Key words: teaching English, critical thinking, creative approach, speaking skills.

One of the most fundamental and positive changes in modern primary education is the decree of the First President of the Republic of Uzbekistan on December 10, 2012 "On measures to further improve the system of learning foreign languages" ” is Resolution No. 1875. Based on this decision, learning foreign languages, mainly English, is taught in the form of game-style lessons and oral speech lessons from the 1st grade of general secondary schools, and from the 2nd grade, the alphabet, reading and grammar are taught. Teaching begins step by step.

For the further development of the study of foreign languages, an incomparable scale of work has been carried out in all areas of education. continuous training in the form of training and oral speech classes was launched. Also, textbooks and teaching-methodical sets designed for these classes were

created. It is worth noting that the games in the complexes created for the first grades are proportional to the age of the children.

Today's demand is to educate mature and independent thinkers, which requires improvement of education in the process of education, development of new directions of work with students and striving for unconventionality. Accordingly, it is necessary to use a variety of methods in educating young students to think, search and consciously acquire knowledge and expand their worldview. One of such new technologies is the formation of critical thinking skills in students. Through critical thinking, primary school students can think independently, freely, analyze, compare, interpret opinions, discuss, defend their ideas and strive for innovations. along with qualifications such as the ability to think logically, worldview, self-awareness, communicative literacy, the ability to feel and enjoy beauty and sophistication, to be mentally and physically healthy, to learn national traditions important features such as absorption and appreciation are developed. This, in turn, ensures that the students of younger age can acquire knowledge in depth and apply it correctly in practice. Accordingly, in order to develop the critical thinking of elementary school students, it is important to design the purpose of the lesson on the basis of clear pedagogical technology. There are many unlearned things in life. Curiosity develops the mind¹. Curiosity leads to discoveries and adventures. By developing the ability to be interested in what is happening, it not only develops critical thinking, but also makes life rich and colorful.

The importance of critical thinking in teaching foreign languages is incomparable, and at present, increasing critical thinking in students is one of the tasks of foreign language teachers. Many different factors can affect students'

¹ Mirman, J. and Tishman, S. (1988) Infusing thinking through connections. Educational Leadership, 45(7), P.64.

critical thinking skills. M. Lipman, S. Norris and R. Ennis, who conducted research in the field of education, presented their approaches to critical thinking. There are no big differences in the definitions given by them, according to L. Elder and R. Paul, critical thinking means the ability of individuals to manage their own thinking and develop appropriate criteria and standards for analyzing their own thoughts². In addition, as noted by V. Maiorana, critical thinking is a process aimed at understanding and evaluating different points of view, solving problems³. The skills necessary to be able to think critically are different. which include observation, analysis, interpretation, reflection, evaluation, inference, explanation, problem solving, and decision-making. The importance of using critical thinking lessons for students of all ages although it is incomparable, we must remember our teaching task and what we need to do to achieve their goal, and we must always take these aspects into account in the teaching process and organize lessons.

Certain aspects of the process of forming critical thinking in students are based on the following principles:

- Coordinating the speed of the reading process;
- Increasing the student's enthusiasm for reading;
- Taking into account previously acquired knowledge;
- Student initiative and commitment support;
- Practical learning;
- Organization of two-way exchange of opinions;
- Setting up the study process; facilitating the process;
- Evaluating the educational process.

² Elder, L. & Paul, R. (1994) Critical thinking: Why we must transform our teaching. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 18(1), P. 34.

³ Maiorana, V. P. (1992). Critical thinking across the curriculum: Building the analytical classroom. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 347511). P.56.

In the process of learning, students' critical thinking creates multifaceted activities, and in the process of transitioning from one type of activity to another, each student develops the ability to determine his personal, specific goal. This goal creates the ground for students to engage in independent, creative activities and is the basis for developing a strict program of action.

The technology of forming critical thinking in students is implemented by pedagogues by performing special types of assignments, independent activities, and their effectiveness is realized with the help of certain criteria. If the educational process is fully directed to the student, organized on the basis of certain principles, taking into account his needs and opportunities, interests, talent, the results of such education, first of all, the student himself, this along with it, it rises to the level of a factor that develops the state, society, and science and production. It is recommended to start using critical thinking in the course of the lesson from a young age⁴. It is very important to adapt the lessons to the age of the children, but it is important to allow them to use their mental abilities as much as possible. Only when the educational process is adapted and improved to the different ways chosen by the students, the foundation for the formation of critical thinking is created.

From the second grade, you can also organize other educational games aimed at mastering grammar. For example, interesting games such as "Who is literate?", "Who is clever?", "Who am I?", "Chain", "Rolling game", "Find the place of the word" are among them. "Who's smart?" game gives a good result in improving spelling literacy. In this case, 5-6 words are written on cardboard, and the words are written correctly and incorrectly. Students are required to find the misspelled word and write it correctly. The winner of the game will be determined

⁴ Lipman, M. (1991). *Thinking in education*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Lipman, M. (2003) *Thinking in education*. New York: Cambridge University Press. P.254.

by the student who writes down the wrongly written words correctly and first. In the current educational process, the student should be the subject. Focusing more on interactive methods will increase the effectiveness of education. One of the most important requirements for English language classes is to teach independent thinking. Research shows that critical thinking is not an innate or naturally formed ability, but it is no exaggeration to say that critical thinking is a taught and learned process. The wide use of activities that develop critical thinking in the course of the lesson requires a high level of skill from the teacher in order for foreign language teachers to provide their students with a quality learning experience.

REFERENCES:

1. Elder, L. & Paul, R. (1994) Critical thinking: Why we must transform our teaching. *Journal of Developmental Education*, 18(1), 34 - 35.
2. Halpern, D. F. (1998). Teaching critical thinking for transfer across domains: Disposition, skills, structure training, and metacognitive monitoring. *American Psychologist*, 53(4).
3. Iriskulov A.T va boshqalar Kids‘ English pupil’s book 2 sinf –Toshkent —O‘zbekiston; 2014
4. Lipman, M. (1991). *Thinking in education*. Cambridge: Cambridge University Press. Lipman, M. (2003) *Thinking in education*. New York: Cambridge University Press
5. Maiorana, V. P. (1992). *Critical thinking across the curriculum: Building the analytical classroom*. (ERIC Document Reproduction Service No. ED 347511).
6. Mirman, J. and Tishman, S. (1988) *Infusing thinking through connections*. *Educational Leadership*, 45(7), 64-65.

